

Study: Investigating Compiler Retargetability

Set of provided hints

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1 Tket

Hint 1: Backend Implementation Guide

To get started with your backend implementation, you'll need to follow the TKET backend implementation guide. This guide contains relevant functions you will need to implement to fulfill the task, as well as the code to the `bell_test` function used later.

Resource: [TKET Custom Backend Guide](#)

Hint 2: List of Necessary Functions

The following functions are required for a complete backend implementation:

- `__init__`
- `_result_id.type`
- `circuit_status`
- `required_predicates`
- `default_compilation_pass`
- `backend_info`
- `tk_to_stim`
- `process_circuits`
- Additionally you will need to set the `rebase_pass` property.

Hint 3: TKET to Stim Function

This function converts a TKET circuit to a Stim circuit. It maps TKET gate operations to their Stim equivalents.

```
def tk_to_stim(self, tkc: Circuit) -> stim.Circuit:
    circuit = stim.Circuit()

    gate_map = {
        OpType.X: "X",
```

```

    OpType.Y: "Y",
    OpType.Z: "Z",
    OpType.H: "H",
    OpType.CX: "CNOT",
}

for command in tkc:
    optype = command.op.type

    if optype in gate_map:
        qbs = [tkc.qubits.index(cast("Qubit", arg)) for arg in command.args]
        circuit.append(gate_map[optype], qbs)
    elif optype == OpType.Measure:
        qb, cb = command.args
        circuit.append("M", [tkc.qubits.index(qb)])
    else:
        raise ValueError(f"Cannot convert optype to MyCircuit: {optype}")

return circuit

```

Hint 4: Result ID Type Function

This property defines the identifier type signature for `ResultHandle` for this backend.

```

@property
def _result_id_type(self) -> _ResultIdTuple:
    """Identifier type signature for ResultHandle for this backend.
    :return: Type signature (tuple of hashable types)
    """
    return (str,)

```

Hint 5: Circuit Status Function

This function returns a `CircuitStatus` reporting the status of the circuit execution corresponding to the `ResultHandle`.

```

def circuit_status(self, handle: ResultHandle) -> CircuitStatus:
    """
    Return a CircuitStatus reporting the status of the circuit execution
    corresponding to the ResultHandle
    """
    if handle in self._cache:
        return CircuitStatus(StatusEnum.COMPLETED)
    raise CircuitNotRunError(handle)

```

Hint 6: Required Predicates Function

This property defines the minimum set of predicates that a circuit must satisfy before it can successfully run on this backend.

```

@property
def required_predicates(self) -> list[Predicate]:
    """
    The minimum set of predicates that a circuit must satisfy before it can

```

```

be successfully run on this backend.
:return: Required predicates.
"""
preds = [
    GateSetPredicate(
        {
            OpType.X,
            OpType.Y,
            OpType.Z,
            OpType.H,
            OpType.CX,
            OpType.Measure,
        }
    ),
]
return preds

```

Hint 7: Rebase Pass

The rebase pass is used to convert circuits into the gate set supported by the backend. This implementation defines custom single-qubit and two-qubit gate decompositions.

```

def sq(a, b, c):
    circ = Circuit(1)
    if c != 0:
        circ.Rz(c, 0)
    if b != 0:
        circ.Rx(b, 0)
    if a != 0:
        circ.Rz(a, 0)
    return circ

rebase = RebaseCustom({OpType.X, OpType.Y, OpType.Z,
                      OpType.H, OpType.CX, OpType.Measure}, Circuit(1), sq)

rebase_pass = rebase

```

Hint 8: Default Compilation Pass Function

This function provides a suggested compilation pass that guarantees the resulting circuit will be suitable to run on this backend.

```

def default_compilation_pass(self, optimisation_level: int = 1) -> BasePass:
    seq = [DecomposeBoxes()] # Decompose boxes into basic gates
    seq.append(self.rebase)
    return SequencePass(seq)

```

Hint 9: Backend Info Function

This property returns metadata about the backend, including its name, version, supported gate set, and architecture.

```

@property
def backend_info(self) -> BackendInfo:
    return BackendInfo(
        "MyBackend",
        "MySimulator",
        "1.0",
        FullyConnected(4),
        {
            OpType.X,
            OpType.Y,
            OpType.Z,
            OpType.H,
            OpType.CX,
            OpType.Measure,
        },
        supports_midcircuit_measurement=False,
        misc={"characterisation": None},
    )

```

Hint 10: Process Circuits Function

This is the core function that submits circuits to the backend for execution and stores results in the cache.

```

def process_circuits(
    self,
    circuits: Iterable[Circuit],
    n_shots: Optional[int] = None,
    valid_check: bool = True,
    **kwargs: KwargTypes,
) -> list[ResultHandle]:
    """
    Submit circuits to the backend for running. The results will be stored
    in the backend's result cache to be retrieved by the corresponding
    get_data method.
    Use keyword arguments to specify parameters to be used in submitting circuits
    See specific Backend derived class for available parameters, from the
    following
    list:
    * 'seed': RNG seed for simulators
    :param circuits: Circuits to process on the backend.
    :param n_shots: Number of shots to run per circuit. None is to be used
        for state/unitary simulators. Defaults to None.
    :param valid_check: Explicitly check that all circuits satisfy all required
        predicates to run on the backend. Defaults to True
    :return: Handles to results for each input circuit, as an interable in
        the same order as the circuits.
    """
    circuit_list = list(circuits)
    if valid_check:
        self._check_all_circuits(circuit_list)
    handle_list = []
    for circuit in circuit_list:
        handle = ResultHandle(str(uuid4()))

        mycirc = self.tk_to_stim(circuit)
        tab = stim.Tableau.from_circuit(mycirc)

```

```

state = tab.to_state_vector()

state *= np.exp(1j * np.pi * circuit.phase)
implicit_perm = circuit.implicit_qubit_permutation()
res_qubits = [implicit_perm[qb] for qb in sorted(circuit.qubits, reverse=
True)]
res = BackendResult(q_bits=res_qubits, state=state)
self._cache[handle] = {"result": res}
handle_list.append(handle)
return handle_list

```

Hint 11: Test Backend

This test function verifies that the backend correctly implements a Bell state circuit.

```

import numpy as np
import pytest

def test_bell() -> None:
    c = Circuit(2)
    c.H(0)
    c.CX(0, 1)
    b = StimStudyBackend()
    c = b.get_compiled_circuit(c)
    h = b.process_circuit(c)
    assert np.allclose(
        b.get_result(h).get_state(), np.asarray([1, 0, 0, 1]) * 1 / np.sqrt(2)
    )

if __name__ == '__main__':
    test_bell()

```

Hint 12: How to Use Stim

This hint explains how to use the Stim library's Tableau functionality to execute circuits and obtain state vectors.

```

import stim

# You can use Tableau, which is compiled from a
# stim circuit instance. Tableau supports the
# operation to_state_vector(), which effectively
# executes the circuit and returns the resulting
# state vector. Keep in mind, this does not work
# with circuits containing Measure gates.

tab = stim.Tableau.from_circuit(mycirc)
state = tab.to_state_vector()

```

2 Qiskit

Hint 1: Backend Implementation Guide

To get started with your backend implementation, you'll need to follow the Qiskit backend implementation guide. This guide contains relevant pointers you will need to implement to fulfill the task.

Resource: [Qiskit Custom Transpiler Guide](#)

Hint 2: List of Necessary Functions

The following functions are required for a complete backend implementation:

- `__init__`
- `target`
- `max_circuits`
- `_default_options`
- `_qiskit_to_stim_circuit`
- `run`

Hint 3: Qiskit to Stim Function

This function converts a Qiskit circuit to a Stim circuit. It maps Qiskit gate operations to their Stim equivalents.

```
def _qiskit_to_stim_circuit(self, qc):
    stim_circuit = stim.Circuit()
    gate_mapping = {
        'h': 'H', 'x': 'X', 'y': 'Y', 'z': 'Z', 'cx': 'CNOT'
    }
    for instr in qc.data:
        op_name = instr.operation.name.lower()

        qubit_ids = [qc.find_bit(q).index for q in instr.qubits]

        if op_name in gate_mapping:
            stim_circuit.append(gate_mapping[op_name], qubit_ids)
        else:
            raise ValueError(f"Unsupported gate: {op_name}")

    return stim_circuit
```

Hint 4: Init Function

The initialization function sets up the backend with its target gate set and default options.

```

def __init__(self):
    super().__init__(name='stim_simulator', description='Stim quantum simulator
backend')
    self._target = self._build_target()
    self._options = self._default_options()

def _build_target(self):
    target = Target("Stim simulator target")
    target.add_instruction(HGate())
    target.add_instruction(XGate())
    target.add_instruction(YGate())
    target.add_instruction(ZGate())
    target.add_instruction(CXGate())
    return target

```

Hint 5: Target Function

This property returns the target object that defines the supported gate set.

```

@property
def target(self):
    return self._target

```

Hint 6: Max Circuits Function

This property defines the maximum number of circuits that can be run in a single job. Returning None means unlimited.

```

@property
def max_circuits(self):
    return None

```

Hint 7: Default Options Function

This class method returns the default options for the backend.

```

@classmethod
def _default_options(cls):
    return Options()

```

Hint 8: Run Function

This is the main execution function that processes circuits and returns a job object.

```

def run(self, run_input, **options):
    if hasattr(run_input, '__iter__') and not isinstance(run_input, str):
        circuits = run_input
    else:
        circuits = [run_input]
    job = PrimitiveJob(self._run, circuits)
    job._submit()
    return job

```

```

def _run(self, circuits):
    results = []
    for circuit in circuits:
        stim_circuit = self._qiskit_to_stim_circuit(circuit)
        tab = stim.Tableau.from_circuit(stim_circuit)
        state = tab.to_state_vector()
        results.append(state)
    return PrimitiveResult(results)

```

Hint 9: Hints for Guide

The backend implementation guide is quite overcrowded. It specifies a very specific example with a lot of parameters, which we do not need here. The task is to create a simple implementation. You do not need to provide parameters when adding gates to your target. You do not need to use a shot-based approach. You can pass an empty options object for the default options. You do not need to specify a value for max circuits. Try to write a converter function from Qiskit to stim circuit, run this circuit on stim, and return the state vector result.

Hint 10: Run Function Return Type

To use the test provided on the task sheet, it is advisable that the run function returns a Job. You can use the `PrimitiveJob` from `qiskit.primitives` combined with a private `_run` function to achieve this in the run function.

```

job = PrimitiveJob(self._run, ...)
job._submit()
return job

```

The private `_run` function should return a `Result`. For this, you can use the `PrimitiveResult` from `qiskit.primitives.containers`.

```

return PrimitiveResult(...)

```

Hint 11: Test Backend

This test function verifies that the backend correctly implements a Bell state circuit.

```

from qiskit import QuantumCircuit

def test_bell() -> None:
    backend = StimStudyBackend()
    qc = QuantumCircuit(2)
    qc.h(0)
    qc.cx(0, 1)
    job = backend.run(qc)
    result = job.result()
    assert np.allclose(
        result[0], np.asarray([1, 0, 0, 1]) * 1 / np.sqrt(2)
    ) or np.allclose(
        result, np.asarray([1, 0, 0, 1]) * 1 / np.sqrt(2))

if __name__ == '__main__':
    test_bell()

```

Hint 12: How to Use Stim

This hint explains how to use the Stim library's Tableau functionality to execute circuits and obtain state vectors.

```
import stim

# You can use Tableau, which is compiled from a
# stim circuit instance. Tableau supports the
# operation to_state_vector(), which effectively
# executes the circuit and returns the resulting
# state vector. Keep in mind, this does not work
# with circuits containing Measure gates.

tab = stim.Tableau.from_circuit(mycirc)
state = tab.to_state_vector()
```

3 ProjectQ

Hint 1: Backend Implementation Guide

ProjectQ does not provide a backend implementation guide. Therefore, you may study implemented ProjectQ backends found on the ProjectQ GitHub page.

Resource: [ProjectQ Backends](#)

Hint 2: List of Necessary Functions

This is the list of functions used in the solution. Your solution may vary.

- `__init__`
- `_reset`
- `is_available`
- `_store`
- `get_result`
- `_run`
- `receive`

Hint 3: ProjectQ to Stim Function

This function converts ProjectQ commands to Stim circuit operations. It handles gate mapping and circuit construction.

```
def _store(self, cmd):
    if self._clear:
        self._stim_circuit = stim.Circuit()
        self._allocated_qubits = set()
```

```

        self._has_run_circuit = False
        self._clear = False
    gate = cmd.gate
    if gate == Allocate:
        self._allocated_qubits.add(cmd.qubits[0][0].id)
        return
    if gate == Deallocate:
        return
    if gate == H:
        qubit_id = cmd.qubits[0][0].id
        self._stim_circuit.append("H", [qubit_id])
    elif gate == X and get_control_count(cmd) == 0:
        qubit_id = cmd.qubits[0][0].id
        self._stim_circuit.append("X", [qubit_id])
    elif (gate == X and get_control_count(cmd) == 1) or
          (gate == NOT and get_control_count(cmd) == 1):
        ctrl_id = cmd.control_qubits[0].id
        target_id = cmd.qubits[0][0].id
        self._stim_circuit.append("CNOT", [ctrl_id, target_id])
    elif gate == Y:
        qubit_id = cmd.qubits[0][0].id
        self._stim_circuit.append("Y", [qubit_id])
    elif gate == Z:
        qubit_id = cmd.qubits[0][0].id
        self._stim_circuit.append("Z", [qubit_id])
    elif gate == CNOT:
        if len(cmd.qubits) == 2:
            ctrl_id = cmd.qubits[0][0].id
            target_id = cmd.qubits[1][0].id
            self._stim_circuit.append("CNOT", [ctrl_id, target_id])
        else:
            raise InvalidCommandError("CNOT gate requires 2 qubits")
    else:
        raise InvalidCommandError(
            f'Gate {gate} not supported by StimBackend.'
        )

```

Hint 4: Init Function

The initialization function sets up the backend and calls the reset method.

```

def __init__(self, verbose=False):
    super().__init__()
    self._verbose = verbose
    self._has_run_circuit = False
    self._reset()

```

Hint 5: Reset Function

This function resets the backend state, clearing the circuit and result data.

```

def _reset(self):
    self._clear = True
    self._stim_circuit = stim.Circuit()
    self._allocated_qubits = set()
    self._result = None

```

Hint 6: Is Available Function

This function checks whether a given command (gate) is supported by the backend.

```
def is_available(self, cmd):
    if has_negative_control(cmd):
        return False
    gate = cmd.gate
    if get_control_count(cmd) == 0:
        return gate in (H, X, Y, Z, Allocate, Deallocate)
    if get_control_count(cmd) == 1:
        return gate in (NOT, X)
    return False
```

Hint 7: Get Result Function

This simple accessor function returns the stored result from the last circuit execution.

```
def get_result(self):
    return self._result
```

Hint 8: Run Function

This function executes the circuit using Stim and stores the result.

```
def _run(self):
    if self._has_run_circuit:
        return
    try:
        if self._verbose:
            print(self._stim_circuit)
        tab = stim.Tableau.from_circuit(self._stim_circuit)
        state = tab.to_state_vector()
        self._result = state
        self._has_run_circuit = True
    except Exception as e:
        raise RuntimeError(f"Failed to run circuit on Stim simulator: {str(e)}")
    from e
```

Hint 9: Receive Function

This function receives commands from ProjectQ and processes them, triggering execution when a FlushGate is encountered.

```
def receive(self, command_list):
    for cmd in command_list:
        if not cmd.gate == FlushGate():
            self._store(cmd)
        else:
            self._run()
            self._clear = True
```

Hint 10: Necessary Gates

ProjectQ does not only require implementation of our backend gate set, it also uses additional gates to process and build circuits. You will need to implement the Allocate, Deallocate, and Flush gates alongside the required gate set. The Flush gate is responsible for triggering the execution of a circuit, while the Allocate gate triggers the allocation of new qubits.

Hint 11: Test Backend

This test function verifies that the backend correctly implements a Bell state circuit using ProjectQ's framework.

```
def test_bell():
    from projectq import MainEngine
    from projectq.ops import H, Measure
    backend = StimBackend(verbose=True)
    engine = MainEngine(backend)
    qubits = engine.allocate_quireg(2)
    H | qubits[0]
    CNOT | (qubits[0], qubits[1])
    engine.flush()
    assert np.allclose (
        backend.get_result(),
        np.asarray([1, 0, 0, 1]) * 1 / np.sqrt(2)
    )

if __name__ == "__main__":
    test_bell()
```

Hint 12: How to Use Stim

This hint explains how to use the Stim library's Tableau functionality to execute circuits and obtain state vectors.

```
import stim

# You can use Tableau, which is compiled from a
# stim circuit instance. Tableau supports the
# operation to_state_vector(), which effectively
# executes the circuit and returns the resulting
# state vector. Keep in mind, this does not work
# with circuits containing Measure gates.

tab = stim.Tableau.from_circuit(mycirc)
state = tab.to_state_vector()
```